

The preliminary study on some living jewels at Bago University Campus and Urban Area of Bago Township

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Abstract

The present study deals with the wild orchids of Bago urban area and Bago University Campus in Bago Township. Bago area is hot weather and high receives of rainfall so a lot of epiphyte (Fern and Orchids) they have grown well on the old big trunk. Most of the collected orchids are epiphyte and terrestrial and studied the whole season. In this recent study (5) genera and (10) species were collected in every season from study area. Collected genera namely *Acampe*, *Aerides*, *Dendrobium*, *Eulophia*, and *Rhynchostylis* were recorded with photograph have taken habitat of orchids in nature. Collected species were classified, identified and described with colour photograph of nature habitats and inflorescences. The morphological characters have been emphasized and artificial keys to the species have been constructed. GPS location system was used and also introduced conservation method for students extra curriculum.

Keywords: Bago Township, native orchids, epiphyte, terrestrial, hydrophyte, artificial key, extra-curriculum

Introduction

The family Orchidaceae is the largest family of among Angiospermae, Monocotyledonae. Some botanist estimated about 35,000 species among flowering plants. They can grow well in Temperate, Subtropical and tropical region but exception of ice capped and deserts. (Dassanayake, 1981)

The recent study is conducted with some native orchids in Bago University and urban area where they grow well naturally on old big tree. Bago Township is located on the east by Daik-U and Waw Township, on the west by Hlegu Township, on the north by Kyaut-ta-ga Township and on the south by Kawa Township it lies between N 17° 20' 12" and E 96° 28' 47". The study sites areas are Bago Urban area, Hpa Yar Kalay, Hpa Yar Gyi village, Wingabaw elephant camp, Road side of cross road to Highway near Wingabaw village, around the Moe-Youne-Gyi Ramsar site and surrounding Village of Bago Township. Some of the specimens were collected from Sa-lu reserved forest. In this recent study, (2) subfamily belong to (3) Tribes (3) Sub tribe (5) genera and (10) species have been recorded form the study area including epiphyte and terrestrial orchids. The classification and taxonomic description of collected specimens are provided with coloured photographic and keys of genera and species are also constructed and GIS recorded.

Methodology

The specimens were collected from Bago urban area and Bago University campus in Bago region. All these specimens were colourful photographed to record their actual habitat and the nature of inflorescence. The collected specimens were classified according to Dressler's classification (R.L. Dressler's (1977) and identified by Seidenfaden (1992) Grant: B (1966): Nantiya Vaddhanaputi (2006) Hooker, J.D.(1954). Seidenfaden and Smitch (1965), Dassanayake, M.D.(1981), Flora of China Vol. 25, (2013) and Flora of Thailand Vol. XI &

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XII. Part I & II (2014) methods. Herbarium specimen well prepared and submitted to Botany Department Yangon University.

Results

In this paper (2) subfamily, (3) tribes, (3) subtribes and (5) genera and (10) species have been collected from study area.

I. Subfamily Epidendroideae

In this recent study only one genus *Dendrobium* of subfamily Epidendroideae was collected from study area.

(1) *Dendrobium*

This genus have more or less elongated cylindrical leafy pseudobulbs at stems, the leaves being generally bifarious, alternate and flat, they differ as in habit, so in size. The flowers are lateral and either solitary, in fascicles or in raceme. The sepals and petals all the segment of the flowers except the lip are nearly uniform in shape the general difference being that of the outer segment or sepal, two lateral sepals are larger than the other and adhere commonly to the side of the column, or usually prolonged into a blunt spur. The lip is always sessile. Pollinia 4 in pairs side by side, quite free, anther 2-celled.

Key to the species of Genus *Dendrobium*

1. Stem long-----2
1. Stem short-----3
 2. Stem slender. Inflorescence with 2-3 flowers. -----4
 2. Stem stout. Inflorescence with many flowers. -----5
3. Stem tuff, ridges. Inflorescence with many flowers. Flower golden yellow. Lip orbicular, yellow patch on the mesochile.----- 1. *Dendrobium aggregatum*
3. Stem stout with white velum, smooth. Inflorescence with 2-3 flowers. Flower white. Lip cordiform with yellow in the basal half, white edges with pink in front. -----
 - 2. *Dendrobium crepidatum*
 4. Stem long and straight. Flower pale purple, about 3.5 cm across lip spatulate, pale yellow with purple vein at the base.----- 3. *Dendrobium aphyllum*
 4. Stem branched. Flower greenish yellow, about 0.5 cm across. Lip longer than the sepal. Lip greenish yellow with small brownish purple dot on hypochile.-----
 - 4. *Dendrobium parcum*
5. Flower creamy white. Lip rounded with two dark blotches on each side of lip.-----
 - 5. *Dendrobium pulchellum*
5. Flower orange yellow. Inflorescence with 4-6 flowers. Lip pouch with incurved edges, with long ciliate vein inside and two maroon blotches or each side at the base.-----
 - 6. *Dendrobium moschatum*

1.1. *Dendrobium aggregatum* Roxb FL iii 477.

Habit

Inflorescence

Flower parts

Myanmar Name - Yadana Shwe Khat (ရတနာရွှေခက်)

Occurrence - Hpa Yar Kalay village, (N 18 ° 55'- E 96° 25')

Ecology - Epiphyte, well grow on the old trunk of mango tree. Flowering period - February- March

1.2 . *Dendrobium crepidatum* Lindl & Paxton

Habit

Inflorescence

Flower parts

Pollinia

Myanmar name - Ga-Naing-Nabayk (ဂနိုင်းနဘေးပေါက်)

Occurrence - Myauk Zamani Wild life Sanctuary, (N 18 ° 4' 83"- E 96° 13' 45")

Ecology - Epiphyte, well grow in tufts on the trunk of the big tree. Flowering period - March-April

1.3. *Dendrobium aphyllum* (Roxb). Fischer

Habit

Inflorescence

Flower parts

Pollinia

Myanmar Name - Lat Tan Shay (လက်တံရှည်)

Occurrence - Myout Zarmani Wild life Sanctuary (N 18 ° 51' 95"- E 96° 14' 6")

Ecology - Epiphyte, well grow on the old trunk, Flowering period-April-May

1.4. *Dendrobium parcum* Rchb.f.

Habit

Flower

Pollinia

Myanmar name - Kyee-Chey (ကျီးချေ)

Occurrence - Myout Zarmani Wild life Sanctuary, (N 18 ° 05' 96"- E 96° 13' 86")

Ecology - Epiphyte, well grow on tree. Flowering period - February-March

1.5. *Dendrobium pulchellum* Roxb ex. Linl. Gen, and SP, Orchid, 82:FL .ind,486

D. dalhousiearum Wall.

Habit

Inflorescence

Flower

Myanmar Name - Sin -ma myat-kwin (ဆင်မမျက်ကွင်း)

Occurrence - Hpa Yar Kalay, Hpa Yar Gyi village and Wingabaw elephant camp (N 18 ° 56'- E 96° 22')

Ecology - Epiphyte, well grown on the trunk of Kok ko. Flowering period-May-Jun

1.6. *Dendrobium moschatum* (Buch. Ham.) S

Habit

Inflorescence

Flower

Myanmar Name - Wah-so -Pan (ဝါဆိုပန်း)

Occurrence - HpaYar Kalay, Hpa Yar Gyi village, Bago urban area. (N 18 ° 56'- E 96° 25')

Ecology - Epiphyte, well grown on the old trunk, Flowering Period-May- June

(II) Subfamily Vandoideae

In this recent study only one genus *Eulophia* under the tribe Cymbidieae was collected from study area.

Genus *Eulophia* posses terrestril, stem tuber or corn. Inflorescence erect, branched. Flower medium. Colour-

Key to the genera of Subtribe Cryptopodineae

- 1. Inflorescence subumbel, spur short, branching, very short. Flower small and medium size -----
-----*Acampe*
- 1. Inflorescence longer than the leaves, unbranching, spur distinct. Flower medium.-----
----- (2)
- 2. Inflorescence large, not like fox tail,spurforward,not flattened-----*Aerides*
- 2. Inflorescence like fox tail, spur backward, laterally compressed----- *Rhychostylis*

2.1. *Eulophia graminea* Lindl.

Habit

Inflorescence

Flower

Myanmar Name - Say-ti-ga-mone (စေတီဂမုန်း)

Occurrence- Bago urban area, Salu reserved forest. (N 17 ° 34' 28"- E 96° 37' 27.8")

Ecology- Terrestrial , lower tropical rain forest. Flowering Period - March-May

3.1. *Acampepapillosa* (Limell) Lindl.

Habit

Inflorescence

Flowers

Myanmar name - Mee- Ma-Laung-Pan (မီးမလောင်ပန်း)

Occurrence - Myanmar, Bago Township, Road side of in Winkabaw village.(N 17° 34' 208" - E 96° 36' 22.8")

Ecology - Epiphyte on the trunk of on Rode side. Alt. 11m. Flowering period - November- December.

4.1. *Aeridesodorata* Lour

Habit

Inflorescence

Flower

Myanmar Name - Sa ka lay pan (စာကလေးပန်း)

Occurrence - Bago urban Area, Myauk Kyaung monastery, Bago township (N 17 ° 27' 40"- E 96° 46' 78")

Ecology-Epiphyte, well grow on the old trunk. Alt. 192 m Flowering period- April-May

5.1. *Rhynchostylis retusa* (L.) Blume Bijdr, 1825, 286 t, fig. 49-Gagnepain 1934

Habit

Inflorescence

Flower

Myanmar Name - Kyaung-me-nant-tha (ကြောင်မြီးနံ့သာ)

Occurrence - Bago urban area, widely distributed in Bago area. (N 17 ° 36' 28.9" - E 96° 36' 40.3")

Ecology -Epiphyte, well grown on the old trunk of rain tree. Alt. 10 m Flowering Period-July to September

Discussion and Conclusion

In this research paper includes (2) subfamilies such as Epidendroideae, Vandoideae. There are (3) Tribes (3) Subtribes, (5) Genera and (10) Species in this recent study.

In subfamily Epidendroideae only one genus *Dendrobium* of subtribe Dendrobineae were recorded in study area. In subfamily Vandoideae, genus *Eulophia* of subtribe Cryptopodiinae was collected in recent study. Three genera such as genus *Acame*, *Aerides*, *Rhynchostylis* of subtribe Sarcanthinae are recorded in recent study. In this research paper (10) Epiphyte and (1) Terrestrial orchids have been recorded. *Dendrobium aphyllum*, *D aggregatum*, *D moschatum*, *D pulchellum* are widely distributed in Bago Division. *D aggregatum*, *D. aphyllum* and *D. moschatum* are native in Myanmar. (Holttum, 1964).

D. crepidatum and *D. parcum* found in Kachin, Chin, Shan, Mandalay, Saging, Thaninthari but this species collected from Bago Division. *Acame papillosa* recorded in Thaninthari but also collected in Bago Division especially grow well and abundant in Taungoo district and *Rhynchostylis retusa* found abundantly in Bago. Some collected species conserved in Bago University by conservation methods for student extra curriculum. Botany students are very interested in practically work and participate in orchids conservation. Nowadays most of the people are interested in the wild orchids for their attractive colour and shape of flowers. Today wild orchids gradually are disappeared by human activities so orchidologists have to find out continuously to know next generation and conserve wild orchid.

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